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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A STABILITY INDICATING HPLC ASSAY METHOD FOR TACROLIMUS IN SEMI-SOLID DOSAGE FORM & BULK DRUG.

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ABSTRACT

In the present study we report the development and validation of reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatographic method for the determination of the tacrolimus in presence of pharmaceutical excipients. The developed method was validated with the guidelines of ICH parameters. Also, the forced degradation studies were performed to develop a stability-indicating high performance liquid chromatographic (HPLC) method for tacrolimus-in the presence of the degradation products. The mobile phase was acetonitrile-water 85:15 (v/v). The calibration plot for the drug was linear in the range 25 – 250 µg/mL was developed on JASCO fully automated HPLC system with Photo-diode array detector at 210 nm wavelength. The method was accurate and precise with limits of detection and quantitation of 4.86 and 14.73 µg, respectively. Mean recovery was 101.05%. In conclusion we report here an simple, precise and accurate developed RP- HPLC method having validated ICH parameters which can scale up to commercial level for the simultaneous quantification of Tacrolimus in dosage form as well as bulk drugs for quality control purpose.

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INTRODUCTION

Tacrolimus (TAC) was discovered in 1984 from the fermentation broth of a Japanese soil sample that contained the bacteria *Streptomyces tsukubaensis*. Tacrolimus, a macrolide agent, inhibits T-lymphocyte activation through a process that is thought to involve it binding to an intracellular protein, FKBP- 12. Tacrolimus is a drug of choice in post-organ transplant patients in organ rejection cases. In the recent past year tacrolimus also widely recommended for the treatment of atopic dermatitis, Psoriasis and skin condition like vitiligo in the form of topical creams. Tacrolimus API falls into BCS Class II having poor water solubility but highly soluble in lipids and other organic solvents. Several dosage forms such as capsules, injection, gels, and ointment are presented in market for clinical uses.

Fig. 1: Structure of Tacrolimus.

There are various reported methods for Tacrolimus estimation in blood are established on LC-MS, HPLC tandem mass spectroscopy and ELISA assay. Literature survey suggests several methods for estimation of tacrolimus alone or in combination with other drugs such as UV spectrophotometry, HPLC and LC-MS. From the table: 1 it was conceived that there is need to establish an analytical method that will be used for routine analytical procedure such as API and semi-solid dosage forms such as gels, Ointments. The major objective behind this study is to develop new, simple, accurate and precise high performance liquid chromatographic method for the estimation of tacrolimus in bulk and semi-solid dosage form. In the present study another objective was to successfully authenticate the developed analytical method with various the analytical performance parameters recommended by the ICH guidelines.

The report of literature methods for HPLC method development is depicted in table no-1

Table no-1: Literature report of Tacrolimus LC method Development.

Sr. No	HPLC mobile phase composition	Column specifications/ Detector	Reported Wavelength	Ref No
1	Acetonitrile (100%) flow rate of 0.9 ml/min	Purospher® 5µm, 250mm X 4.6mm, Photodiode array	213nm 5.3 min	(1, 2)
2	Aetonitrile and water (80:20 v/v). flow rate 0.6 mL/min	LiChrospher100, RP-18e, 5 µm, 125 × 4 mm column (BGB Analytik AG; Boeckten, Switzerland. Temp- 35 O c UV170U detector	210nm.	(3)
3	Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and acetonitrile. flow rate of 1.0 ml/min.	XDB C8 column (particle size 5 µm) UV detector	210nm.	(4)
4	Acetonitrile and water Flow rate- 1ml/min.	Inertsil ODS-3, C18, 250×4.6 mm, 5 µm stainless steel column (GL Sciences Inc., Torrance, CA, USA). Column temperature- 25°C.	213nm	(5)
5	Acetonitrile: deionized water: isopropyl alcohol (60:30:10v/v) adjusted to pH of 3 by phosphoric acid Flow rate- 1ml/min	C18 column (Macherey– Nagel, 4.6×150 mm, 10-µm particle size). column temperature-60°C	215nm	(6)

6	ACN/water 70:30 Flow rate 0.9 ml/min	Inertsil ODS-2 5 mm C18 column Temp- 60°C	214 nm.	(7)
7	Acetonitrile 100%, flow rate—0.5 ml/min,	LiChrospher® 100 RP-18 (5 µm), 4/120 mm	213 nm,	(8)
8	Mixture of acetonitrile/buffer [80:20 (v/v)]. Buffer Composition: 50-mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 0.1% w/v triethylamine, 0.25% w/v octane-1-sulphonic acid, and 0.25% w/v heptane-1-sulphonic acid with pH 2.5± 0.1. Flow rate- 2 ml/min.	Zorbax C-8 (4.6×250 mm and 5 µ) Column temperature-60°C,	210 nm.	(9)
9	ACN/water mobile phase at 0.9 ml/min	Inertsil ODS 2 Column column oven temperature at 60°C,		(10)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tacrolimus was generously donated by Biocon India Ltd Bangalore, Marketed formulation of Tacrolimus ointment (Topgraf from GSK India) was procured from a local pharmacy. Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was bought from the Rankem Chemicals (INDIA). Other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. Distilled water was obtained from water purification system ELIX 03 (Millipore).

Apparatus and Chromatographic Conditions

The HPLC system consisted of a Quaternary gradient Pump (JASCO PU 2089 Plus), Auto sampler (JASCO AU-2055 Plus), and Photodiode array detector (JASCO MD-2018 Plus, Seoul, South Korea). Chromatographic separation was done on a Phenomenex Luna® 5µm, 150mm X 4.6mm. The mobile phase is having a structure of acetonitrile & water in the ratio of 85:15 which was propelled at a continuous flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The eluent was detected using Photodiode array detector at a wavelength of 210 nm. The column was maintained at temperature 60 °C and an injection volume of 20µl was injected. Mobile phase used in this study was filtered through 0.45µm Ultipor® Nylon 6 membrane (Pall Lifescience, Bengaluru) filter to use. With the optimised parameters, retention time (tR) of TAC was near around 3.504 min.

Standard Solution and Calibration Graphs

The standard stock solution was prepared by weighing 10mg of Tacrolimus and dissolved in 10ml acetonitrile to get clear solution and the concentration of 1000 µg/ml. Suitable and appropriate dilutions were made to bend the final concentration 25, 50 100, 150, 200, 250 µg/ml.

SAMPLE SOLUTION PREPARATION

The contents of 3 ointment tubes were removed and placed in a glass beaker, and an amount of ointment equivalent to 10mg of Tacrolimus was taken and dissolved in the 100 ml of acetonitrile. The stock solution was diluted to obtain the final concentration of 100 µg/ml of Tacrolimus.

METHOD VALIDATION

The developed method was successfully authenticated in terms of various parameters such as specificity, precision, accuracy, linearity and range, LOD, LOQ, and ruggedness, etc. Percentage relative standard deviation values for all the parameters were calculated. The proposed HPLC method was validated as per ICH guidelines.

RESULTS& DISCUSSION:

Fig: 2 shows the chromatogram of Tacrolimus after setting up the chromatographic conditions.

Fig. 2: Chromatogram of Tacrolimus.

The results of calibration curve are presented in fig 3.

Fig. 3: Standard curve of Tacrolimus.

Active Content: The results are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Assay of market formulation.

Formulation	Actual concentration	(µg/ml) % Tacrolimus
Topgraf (GSK)	100%	99.03

Method Validation study

Specificity:

Specificity is the ability of a method to differentiate between the analyte(s) of interest and other components that are present in the sample. Various studies are proposed to estimate the degree of interference, if any, which can be attributed to other analytes, impurities, degradation products, reagent "blanks" and excipients. This proposed studies can provide the analyst with a degree of certainty that the response detected is due to the single analyte of importance. Specificity term is occasionally used interchangeably with the "selectivity". The argument over which term is more correct is one of semantics. Although there is some dissention, the term "specificity" has been adopted by the regulatory guidance documents and should be used to prevent further confusion.

Accuracy

Accuracy is the confidence in agreement between the accepted true value or a reference value and the actual result achieved. Accuracy studies are generally calculated by determining the recovery of a spiked sample of the analyte into the matrix of the sample to be analysed. Accuracy is measured in drug substances by spiking known amounts of the analyte into the excipients and calculating the percent recovered. In our case accuracy was established by addition of three different quantities [Low, Medium, and High] of the TAC to the sample solution comprising the concentration of 150 µg/ml. The results are presented in table 3.

Linearity:

Linearity in a simple term is a capability of a method to achieve test results that are directly proportional to the sample concentration over a given range. In chromatographic separation techniques such as High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), the liaison between sample concentration and detector response (peak area or height) is used to get this quantification. It is a requirement that a minimum of five concentration ranges must be examined and a plot of the detector response vs. the sample concentration should be generated. Generally a graphical representation of the linearity data to be produced. The percent y-intercept is calculated by dividing the y-intercept by the detector response at the nominal concentration expressed as a percentage. For single-point calibration, this value should be less than 1-2% to guarantee accurate results.

Table no 3: Various analytical parameters of developed method.

Parameters	Tacrolimus
Linear Range (µg/ml)	25-250 mg
Retention time (min)	3.504
Slope	712.34
Intercept	9367.2
Standard deviation of slope	1.21%
Standard deviation of intercept	0.988%
Limit of Detection (µg/ml)	4.86
Limit of Quantification (µg/ml)	14.73
Linear equation	$Y=712.34x + 9367.2$
R ² value	0.9995

Precision

Precision in chromatographic separations is a extent of the capability of the developed method to produce reproducible results. Generally precision of a method is judged using three single determinations for repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility. Intermediate precision is one of the measure of the performance of the method where samples are tested and linked using different analysts, different equipment, different days, etc. This study is a measure of inter-lab unpredictability and is a measure of the precision that can be anticipated within a laboratory. Precision was checked by carrying out Intraday and Inter-day determination concentration on three different concentrations as presented in table 4. Repeatability was determined on 6 replicate of each concentration of the standard solution. The results are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Summary of various validation parameters.

Parameters	Tacrolimus
Recovery (%)	98.43-103.67
Repeatability (RSD, n=6)	0.762-1.625
Specificity	specific
Precision Range (CV)	
Intra-day (n=3)	0.411-1.46
Inter-day (n=3)	0.13-1.94

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The LOD is the least amount of analyte that can be identified, but not essentially quantitated using a given method. This parameter is important in the use of limit tests as it sets the level below which the method cannot function. The LOQ is the lowest level that an analyte can estimate with any degree of certainty. The limit of Detection (LOD) and limit of Quantification (LOQ) of the developed method were determined by injecting increasingly low concentrations of the standard solutions using the developed RP-HPLC method. The LOD for Tacrolimus found to be 4.86 μ g/ml. and the LOQ was 14.74 μ g/ml for Tacrolimus.

Robustness

Robustness is a measure of the performance of a method when minor and considered variations are made to the method conditions. The intent of this validation parameter is to identify which, if any, of the method conditions are the most critical to the successful performance of the method. The ruggedness of the method was determined by carrying out the experiment on different instruments. The average %RSD values with two different instruments were 1.32 and 1.46 respectively.

Solution Stability:

The stability of the standard and sample solutions were observed at 0 h, 2 h, 4 h, 8 h, 12 h and 24 h. The results showed no significant difference was noted in the area of the peaks compared to the initial peak area (within $\pm 2\%$ for TAC). All this established that the test sample was stable at room temperature for 24 hours

Forced degradation studies:

Forced degradation studies mainly involves exposing the sample to a range of stressed conditions to further evaluate the specificity of degradation products. In forced degradation studies, the drug substance and the combined excipients were individually exposed to the stressed conditions. These may include but are not limited to, heat, light, acidic media, alkaline media, and oxidative environments. Forced degradation is frequently evaluated with not more than 20% degradation of the drug substance, though more may be acceptable pertaining to the drug properties. There should be a rational efforts to be made to degrade samples in order to recognize possible degradation products. If the intended experiments do not show any considerable degradation, the strength and/or exposure time of the stress condition may be increased, but degradation is not required for every condition studied. Table 5 shows used conditions for forced degradation studies.

Table no-5: Conditions used for forced degradation study:

Forced Degradation	Condition
Acidic	24 hour in 1N HCl Solution
Basic	24 hr in 1N NaOH Solution
Oxidative	24 hour in H ₂ O ₂ Solution
Heat	24 hour in 105 ^o C
Light	1-hour exposure UV lamp (200-300nm)

Acid Degradation:

Fig 4: Chromatogram of Tacrolimus in Acid degradation condition.

Base Degradation**Fig 6: Chromatogram of Tacrolimus in Oxidative degradation condition.**

Heat treatment

Fig 7: Chromatogram of Tacrolimus in Heat degradation condition.

Photostability

Fig 8: Chromatogram of Tacrolimus in Photo degradation condition.

The reversed-phase Liquid Chromatography method designated in this paper was developed to provide a quick quality control determination of Tacrolimus in ointment and API. The proposed method is less time consuming and modest. Method was appraised for their accuracy and precision. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines. All samples were analysed by using the chromatographic conditions described. Linearity of the detector responses was determined by formulating calibration graphs. The linearity of the peak response versus concentration was studied from 25 to 250 µg/ml. The archetypal linear equation was $Y = 712.34X + 9367.2$ and a correlation coefficient (r) is 0.9995. Recovery study was achieved in triplicate and average recovery was found in range of 98.43%-103.67% demonstrating that the proposed method for the determination of Tacrolimus in ointment was highly accurate. The precision is expressed as the %RSD and it was found in the range of 0.13- 1.940. The Inter-day and intra-day precision were 0.13-1.940 and 0.411-1.46 respectively. In the forced degradation studies it was found that the TAC is stable only heat treatment i. e heating for 105^o C for 24 hours. There is no change in RT observed. A small change in forced degradation study was observed that is in case of Photostability. We have observed a small extra peak before the retention of tacrolimus at 2.23 min. The tacrolimus was completely unstable in acidic, Basic and oxidative conditions. The structural modifications were observed that resulted in a different retention time, which nowhere matches with RT of tacrolimus.

CONCLUSION

An suitable and rapid RP- HPLC method has been established for an estimate of Tacrolimus in Ointment dosage form. The assay provides a linear response across a wide range of concentrations. Low intraday and inter-day %RSD together with excellent recoveries. The proposed method is simple, economic fast, accurate and precise for the simultaneous quantification of Tacrolimus in dosage form as well as bulk drugs for quality control purpose. The future work can be possible to apply and establish this developed method into plasma to quantify the tacrolimus for *in-vivo* study.

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AUTHORS' STATEMENT:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS:

TAC	- Tacrolimus
RP-HPLC	- Reversed Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography
ICH	- International Conference of Harmonisation.
API	- Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients
LOD	- Limit of Detection
LOQ	- Limit of Quantification
tR	- Retention time
UV	- Ultra Violet
LC-MS	- Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy
ELISA	- Enzyme Linked Immunosorbant Assay
BCS	- Biopharmaceutical classification
RSD	- Relative standard Deviation

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